

Creating and delivering engagement for a national, cross-institutional, multi-disciplinary research programme: Lessons for practitioners

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Abstract

In this paper we reflect on our experience as members of a well-funded, well-integrated engagement programme within a multi-institutional, multi-disciplinary climate-change research initiative. After describing the goals, structure, and activities of the programme, we analyse the obstacles we faced, which we classify into two types: 1) definitional and process challenges, including both conflicting assumptions about the meaning of engagement and incompatible timelines of science and engagement; and 2) challenges of political and institutional context. From this we derive lessons for similarly placed practitioners. These include:

- High-quality engagement requires a great deal of ‘invisible’ preparatory and maintenance work, including, but not limited to, education of colleagues and managers with little or no knowledge about engagement;
- When those with little engagement expertise nonetheless have power over engagement-practitioner activities, education is vital but may not be sufficient to protect the integrity of the engagement effort;
- Early work to establish explicit guidelines and processes for how engagement is overseen may (or may not) be protective;
- The political and institutional context of the engagement programme will likely precipitate a power structure that shapes the challenges faced and the likelihood of overcoming them.

Key Words

Public engagement; political context of engagement; engagement definition; engagement strategy; engagement theory and practice; reflexive science engagement

Key Messages

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The political and institutional context of the engagement programme will likely precipitate a power structure that shapes the challenges faced and the likelihood of overcoming them.

1. Introduction

In 2013, the New Zealand (NZ) government, established National Science Challenges (NSCs) to “respond to the most important, national-scale issues and opportunities identified by science stakeholders and the New Zealand public” and to produce “major and enduring benefits for all New Zealanders” (Ministry of Business, Innovation & Employment, 2013, p. 3). The resultant eleven cross-disciplinary, collaborative research programmes are primarily focused on human health and living conditions, environmental issues, and science for technological innovation. The Challenges were also expected to deliver “public outreach, communication, public engagement, and education activities” (Ministry of Business, Innovation & Employment, 2013, p. 14).

The authors of this paper were involved in design and delivery of the Engagement Programme for one of these NSCs, called the Deep South Challenge (DSC), which was focused on New Zealand-relevant climate change processes and impacts. The paper draws on our experiences starting in 2014, when we were invited to join the conceptualization of engagement within the DSC, and prior to it being funded for the first five years (June 2014–2019). It reflects our experiences establishing and embedding engagement in the DSC until 2018, shortly after one of us (RS) stepped down from the leadership of the Engagement Programme (due to the administrative burden associated with the position, rather than any differences of opinion with the leadership; she remained a member of the Engagement Team for another year). In 2019, the DSC was funded for another five years and is ongoing at the time of writing. While our work provided a foundation for the current programme, this paper does not refer to or reflect the current DSC engagement activities or direction.

After an introduction and overview of the DSC, the DSC Engagement Programme, and its main activities during the period covered here, we explore the nature of the challenges we encountered in delivering engagement as part of the DSC. Our broader experience in this field suggests that some of these challenges exist within most science research programmes, regardless of their commitment and approach to communication and engagement.

In addition to our own experiences and associated documents, this paper draws on a number of interviews with those involved with the DSC as well as other National Science Challenges. New Zealand's research community is a small one; therefore, in order to protect the anonymity of our informants, we do not explicitly reference these interviews in the paper. Where appropriate, relevant interviewees have been shown the full manuscript and have approved the representation of their ideas in this paper. We also draw on survey data associated with our initial pilot phase and individual event evaluations.

1.1 The Deep South Challenge (DSC)

While the NSCs were designed to be multi-institutional, they are “hosted” by a single institution, which holds the budget and contracts the other participant institutions and researchers. NSC budgets range from \$30 – 106 M over ten years (Ministry of Business, Innovation & Employment, n.d.). In the case of the DSC, this institution is a Crown Research Institute (CRI), a type of state-owned research organization (discussed further in Section 4).

In 2015, the DSC was contracted to deliver on the following mission:

This Challenge will enable New Zealanders to adapt, manage risk, and thrive in a changing climate. Working with our communities and industry, we will guide planning and policy to enhance resilience and exploit opportunities. This will be

built on improved predictions of future climate, supported by new understanding of Antarctic and Southern Ocean processes. The Challenge will focus on the effects of a changing climate on key climate sensitive economic sectors, infrastructure and natural resources.

(The Deep South, 2014, p. 3)

The Objective of the DSC, set by the NZ government, is “to understand the role of the Antarctic and Southern Ocean in determining our climate and our future environment.” The DSC inherited from an earlier, unsuccessful, proposal a focus on Antarctic and Southern Ocean physical science research to inform climate impacts in New Zealand. The Challenge was thus based around a strong focus on Antarctic and Southern Ocean science, coupled with impacts research for New Zealand. The scope of the DSC was interpreted by the DSC Governance Board and the initial contracting institutions to exclude mitigation-focused research, while including impacts and adaptation. This provided some challenges from an engagement perspective, since, as Moser (2017), says “in practical reality the communication of adaptation blends with that of the science and mitigation” (p. 7).

A key objective of the DSC was the development of New Zealand’s first Earth System Model (NZESM), based in the DSC’s host institution, which was intended to enable climate scientists to make more accurate predictions about the impacts and implications of climate change across New Zealand under different conditions. The NZESM and DSC Engagement were envisioned as linked, made explicit in the Engagement Strategy as follows:

The Deep South Challenge will use this model and its associated projections and projects to assist sectors and communities across the country to make better-informed decisions in areas that will be impacted by climate change.

(Salmon & Goven, 2017, p. 4)

Development of the NZESM would, however, take several years. Parallel with this, DSC funding was also directed toward research that could either inform the NZESM or provide greater understanding of the implications of new insights that would presumably be generated by the NZESM. The Challenge therefore committed to contributing to a wide range of observational and analytical climate-change research, as well as engagement with key communities, stakeholders and end-users, including New Zealand's indigenous community: Māori whānau (extended families), hapū (subtribes), iwi (tribes) and businesses. In order to deliver on this research and engagement commitment, five integrated DSC programmes were established: Processes and Observation, Earth System Modelling, Impacts and Implications, Vision Mātauranga and Engagement. The leader of each of these programmes sat on the Science Leadership Team (SLT), which in turn reported to the Governance Board. The DSC Governance Board was composed of nine members, weighted toward corporate and managerial, rather than science and research, expertise. There was also a commitment for all Challenges to report annually to the governmental funding body, the Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment (MBIE).

DSC funding in the first five years supported researchers from a range of organisations around NZ, including Crown Research Institutes, universities and independent research organisations. They also represented a wide range of disciplinary expertise and research methods: from highly quantitative computer modelling, to observational field work, to environmental social science, economics, engagement research and Mātauranga Māori, a term used to describe Māori ways of knowing (see Hikuroa (2017) and references therein).

1.2 The DSC Engagement Programme

The authors of this paper were responsible for different aspects of the conceptualisation, development, and delivery of the first iteration of the DSC Engagement Programme. As researchers of public engagement with science (PES), we were also interested in the opportunity to apply insights from PES research to a large, national, multidisciplinary, multi-institutional research programme that had prioritised engagement and included it at strategic and management levels. Unlike in other National Science Challenges, and many analogous programmes internationally, the Challenge was structured so that Engagement had (in theory at least) the same strategic influence and opportunities as the physical and social science programmes.

We focused initially on establishing and gaining support for a more ambitious and critically informed engagement programme. This included (a) defining the primary goal of engagement as being connected to informing decision-making (rather than, for example, getting people engaged in science for its own sake, or generating enthusiasm for a particular research endeavour); (b) identifying and increasing opportunities for both potentially critical dialogue (in addition to one-way communications) and forms of co-production (specifically, enabling affected communities to shape research priorities); and (c) building capacity and capability in engagement about climate change. By co-production, we mean an approach to research in which communities who are meant to benefit from, or who otherwise will be affected by, the research become partners in formulating, designing, carrying out, analysing, and reporting the research (see Willyard et al., 2018). Co-production here is not taken to mean researchers working at the direction of, and funded by, financially interested and socially powerful parties. This common practice may be better termed ‘captured’ rather than ‘co-produced’ science. We are also not using ‘co-production’ in the sense developed by Sheila Jasanoff and others in Science and Technology

Studies to refer to the deep and wide social processes through which science (and technology) and social order mutually constitute one another (see Jasanoff, 2004).

We developed the image in Figure 1 to represent and explain to our colleagues and others our concept of the role of engagement within the Challenge. This included the role of the researchers as listeners and learners as well as experts, and the role of different publics as holding expertise as well as being informed by it. The diagram simplifies DSC engagement foci down to three key actors: people involved with the DSC, people whose decision-making could be informed by DSC research ('end-users'), and a 'general public' for whom the goal was to raise awareness of potential decision-making about climate change of relevance to them, but who would be unlikely to directly use data created by the DSC.

Figure 1: Schematic of the role of Engagement within the DSC. While the diagram focuses on the three key actors, the fainter circles represent the recognition that the distinctions are not clear cut: statuses can shift and people can represent different positions depending on the issue or context.

The DSC Engagement Strategy, developed in consultation with the Challenge Director and members of the SLT and approved by the Board, included four key foci: (A) engagement between the Challenge and key end-users ; (B) engagement between the Challenge and general public, (C) the creation of opportunities for relevant communities to inform the research priorities of the Challenge; and (D) capacity- and capability-building in engagement about climate change (indicated by the circles around the three key end-users in Figure 1). The first two foci (public engagement and end-user engagement) are well-established in engagement and communication practice, although it is worth noting that the identification of key end-users in and of itself can be highly political. The third (informing research priorities) has increasingly become a focus of public engagement (e.g. National Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement, 2019; Ross, 2019), stimulated by literature in PES (see the special issue introduced by Bauer, 2014) and the more recent field of Research into Responsible Innovation (RRI) (see the special issue introduced by Jakobsen et al., 2019). We added capacity- and capability-building as a result of our pilot phase, which identified a strong desire in NZ for information and engagement about local climate impacts and climate change that could not be met by the number of experts in NZ with both the appropriate knowledge and the engagement skills, as well as the time, interest or mandate to carry out this engagement work. We therefore decided that investment in capability- and capacity-building about climate change engagement (specifically about the impacts and implications of climate change for NZ) was a key gap/opportunity that the DSC Engagement Programme could help fill.

The overarching goal of the Engagement Programme, as expressed in the Engagement Strategy, was to improve New Zealanders' ability and capacity to make decisions informed by DSC-related research. This was delivered by focusing on six work areas related to: ensuring that

research responds to New Zealanders' needs, broad and public engagement, targeted sector engagement, capability-building in engagement, evaluation, and internal reporting.

We established a Technical Advisory Committee on Engagement (TACE), from which guidance and approval was sought on major engagement initiatives, and assisted in the creation of a Representative User Group (RUG), which was intended to be a channel to build relationships between decision makers and the DSC. Approval of the Engagement Strategy enabled formal funding of the NZ\$1.7M Engagement Programme and appointment of other members of the Engagement Team including an Engagement Coordinator, Partnerships Director and Evaluation Director. All of these roles were part-time, with the expectation that the majority of engagement activities themselves would be outsourced via contracts. (This decision was taken partly due to the lower direct cost of hiring contractors rather than employing additional salaried staff; in the latter case, the DSC would also be required to pay hefty overheads to the CRI or university in which the staff were based.)

The DSC Engagement Programme funded, developed, or sponsored a wide range of activities and initiatives during the period under discussion. Activities with budgets up to NZ\$20k were generally developed and delivered by external partners. Scoping and funding for these occurred through an Expression of Intent (EoI) process, which was then refined through negotiation with the DSC Engagement team. Through this process, applicants were asked to identify how the proposed project would deliver on the goal and objectives of the Engagement Programme, as well as their overall goal of the project, geographic location, demographic, what would constitute “success” and how they planned to determine if the project had been successful. The DSC Engagement team also agreed to strategic sponsorships (e.g. conferences with key sectoral communities) in exchange for the opportunity to present or engage with delegates. Finally, the

DSC Engagement team itself produced key communications for the DSC as a whole (such as reports for end-users and the public, the website, e-newsletters, and social media), ran capacity-building workshops and worked to establish new relationships and collaborations. Individual DSC researchers also carried out their own project-specific engagement. This was later formalised and supported by the Engagement Team through a Communications and Engagement (C&E) Plan for each project. We also supported engagement associated with a Dialogue process led by the Impacts and Implications programme, discussed in more detail below.

2. Implementing DSC Engagement

2.1 Visible Work: Engagement and Capacity-Building Activities

‘Visible’ work encompasses those outward-facing activities typically seen as the *raison d’être* of an engagement programme. Table 1 conveys the scope of the activities delivered during this period. It is not an exhaustive list, but is indicative of the range of activities that were supported by the DSC Engagement Programme: from static, one-way, information resources (level 1) to activities in which participants collaborated on the development of the DSC research agenda (level 4).

Table 1: A sampling of DSC engagement activities in at different levels of engagement (not comprehensive)

Nature of engagement	Example activities funded	Intended audience (CB: indicates capacity/capability-building in climate-change engagement)
Level 1: information transfer. no conversation	New Zealand Geographic Magazine feature article and online portal	Public – with an interest in sciences; DSC stakeholders
	Contribution to Aotearoa New Zealand Science Journalism Fund to stimulate articles related to climate adaptation	Public via mainstream media; DSC stakeholders CB: journalists
	Mainstream news articles, radio interviews & podcasts	News consumers with an interest in climate change
	DSC website & social media, infographic, newsletters	DSC community and associates
Level 2: information transfer but with conversation/interaction	Video series with Facebook/Youtube influencer. 2.5M views with considerable social media interaction	Young adult popular audience CB: influencer and videographer
	Art+science exhibition, panel discussion & podcast (Auckland Museum / Radio NZ) plus one-on-one conversations in marquee at event	Wide public audience. Included opportunity for one-on-one conversations in an event marquee.
	Museum exhibition (Far From Frozen) and associated panel discussion	Families and event visitors CB: Antarctic researchers who volunteered at exhibition
	Conference presentations and sponsorship eg, Water NZ, Environmental Defence Society Climate Change and Business Conference, local government	Targeted conference audiences and specialist communities
	Infographic about adaptation for urban planners, developed with local and regional government	Urban planners and council staff who co-developed the infographic
Level 3: interaction in which participants can explore implications of the information	Workshop for Water NZ data modellers about DSC	Specialist audience - water engineers
	Collaborative design 'hack' events - Climathon - focused on adaptation solutions	Hackathon participants including designers, activists, engineers,
	Sponsorship of, and participation in, regional roadshow, led by the Ministry for the Environment to gain feedback on new guidelines for coastal management	researchers, researcher communities (planners, residents, business, industry)
	Climate Adaptation Ambassadors' Workshop: Steering research through to policy and action	local and regional government employees and consultants interested in adaptation pathways
	Alexandra Community Climate Change Forum	Local stakeholders residents, planners, council
Level 4: participants inform the research agenda	Deep South Dialogues	issue-based specialist communities including insurance and banking, water, transport and coastal communities.
Capability-building only.	Science media training for DSC researchers	CB: DSC researchers
	Colloquium on communication of climate change	CB: people who communicate about climate change professionally

At the knowledge-transfer end of the spectrum (level 1), we collaborated with well-respected public media outlets New Zealand Geographic and Radio New Zealand as well as supporting the new Aotearoa New Zealand Science Journalism Fund, which invested in long-form journalism on designated topics. Our sponsorship in the first year funded in-depth reporting on climate change by two journalists, one associated with a national news outlet and the other with a major regional newspaper (*2017 Funding Round*, n.d.).

On several occasions, an interactive or dialogue component (level 2) was incorporated into a primarily one-way activity as a result of the DSC partnership. Examples include public panel discussions associated with two art exhibitions, a museum exhibition and a play; discussions with local council officials during the development of an infographic about local climate impacts and adaptation, and discussions with delegates at conferences that we had targeted as being DSC stakeholders (e.g. conferences about climate aimed respectively at business and local government managers).

We also collaborated on a project that took a young female social media star to Antarctica. The short videos constituted one-way information transfer, but they sparked discussion in comment sections that added an interactive dimension. We took a risk in this collaboration since we (a) had no control over what she would say and (b) were trying to move the focus of climate change conversations away from Antarctica and to New Zealand. However, with a following of 10 million on Facebook at the time of production, and an estimated 2.5M views across five short online videos, we felt this was a unique opportunity to reach a young audience who have been identified as being of strategic importance in climate change communication (Ojala & Lakew, 2017), but who were not the primary audience of our other engagement channels. The risk paid off: *Jamie's World on Ice* sent a very strong message about the reality of climate change with the

film director being acknowledged with awards from both the Science Communicators Association of New Zealand and the NZ\$100,000 Prime Minister's Science Communication Prize.

Level 3 events are those where participants could explore the implications of DSC research. This included a workshop designed for Water NZ data modellers (Water NZ is an organisation for those working in the drinking water, stormwater, and wastewater sectors); participation in a national roadshow (and associated discussions) about new government guidelines on coastal management; and a local community event focused on the implications of climate change for that region.

Level 4 activities are intended to give participants the opportunity to inform the research agenda and form research partnerships. Although the DSC ran stakeholder workshops to inform their funding proposals prior to both funding rounds (2014, 2019), these fell outside the remit of the Engagement Programme and are therefore not included here. We focus instead on the Deep South Dialogues (Dialogues), which were the closest example of co-production within the DSC.

Led by the Impacts and Implications Programme, with assistance from the Engagement Programme, the Dialogues aimed “to develop a shared understanding of key issues, to map current knowledge about them, to identify creative ideas to address them, and to pose well-formulated research questions” (*The Dialogues*, n.d.). The dialogue process involved two facilitated full-day meetings, approximately six weeks apart, for around 20 participants from industry, local and central government, the research community and civil society, with a goal to have a mix of expertise, involve at least two indigenous participants, and generally achieve a diversity of gender, age and culture in the room. Participants attended as individuals, rather than

as representatives of their organisations. The facilitated process culminated in participants developing and prioritising a shortlist of clearly defined and high-priority research questions, which were circulated to involved or recommended researchers within a request for proposal process. The intention of the Dialogue programme was to fund two to three high-quality proposals per Dialogue, of around \$100,000 per question, for which the DSC had a ring-fenced budget (approved by the Board). Each Dialogue (including proposed research questions) was also summarised in a publicly available report (Motu Economic and Public Policy Research, n.d.). Five Dialogues were held in total, focusing on 1) insurance, coastal housing, and climate adaptation; 2) climate change and storm water and wastewater infrastructure; 3) flood-prone communities and sea-level rise; 4) drought and climate change adaptation; and 5) urban and freight transport. The Engagement Programme worked alongside this process by aiding in nominating participants for the workshops, the Partnerships Director actively participating in the workshops, organising briefings related to the outputs, and nurturing the ongoing relationships with participating end-users.

We also created or instigated visible activities associated with our goal to build capacity and capability in climate change engagement. This included two workshops for this purpose, as well as supporting DSC researchers to participate in media training events carried out by others. To inform the workshops, we distributed a survey around a range of groups and individuals involved with climate change engagement in different capacities, asking if they would value professional development in climate change engagement and, if so, their preferred content and format. The survey led to the creation of the two workshops: the first, in May 2018 (see *Climate Adaptation Ambassadors' Workshop*, n.d.), was designed for local government, policy and business professionals interested in practical pathways and policy levers related to climate adaptation. The

second, held in November of the same year, was designed for people who communicate about climate change professionally, and included artists, writers, researchers, policymakers, educators and advocates. This event was also recorded and captured graphically (*Communicating Climate*, 2019).

2.2 Invisible Work

In addition to the tangible, visible activities discussed above, we did an enormous amount of ‘invisible’ work, which was fundamental to creating the infrastructure that made the rest of this work possible. We divide this work into three categories: pre-operational, operational, and capability- and capacity-building.

Pre-operational work focused on securing in-principle commitment to funding an engagement programme with our proposed orientation. This included, for example, the multiple meetings that led to engagement becoming embedded at a management level in the original funding application; the development, writing and presenting of the engagement strategy once the DSC had been funded; and advocating for the role of engagement within the DSC and across the National Science Challenges and national science communication community more broadly.

Operational work involved creating the outward-facing infrastructure required for our concept of engagement to occur. In addition to creating funded engagement positions and advisory committees, this involved (a) *cultivating key relationships* between DSC representatives and key stakeholders such as government officials, heads of industry associations and community leaders. It was also necessary to (b) *build operational channels*, such as an external website and a mechanism to interact with DSC researchers. This included developing accessible design content that could be applied to a variety of outputs including a DSC infographic, web navigation and

presentation templates. Other invisible operational work involved (c) *advocating and demonstrating how to “walk the talk”* in our commitment to engagement. Examples include making the \$2M DSC contestable funding accessible to engagement proposals as well as more traditional science research. This opportunity led to the successful funding (\$300k) of a research project that explored the role of culture in public engagement about climate change (Munshi et al., 2018).

We did not anticipate that such invisible work would also be needed in relation to the climate-change engagement community whose work we expected to support. When we first conceptualised the Engagement Programme, we had not realised that the community most likely to apply for engagement funding had an understanding of engagement that did not match what we were looking for. The invisible work that we performed in response to this is discussed in more detail in Section 3.1: “The challenge of conflicting assumptions about engagement”.

Different approaches were used to build engagement capability and capacity within different communities. For example, the structure and criteria in the EoI process, and associated negotiation, were targeted primarily at science communicators and communication professionals. It was designed both as a mechanism to receive engagement ideas and also as a channel to build understanding about, and encourage applicants to create tangible outputs related to, our engagement objectives. We also created training videos and scheduled Zoom meetings aimed at people who were interested in applying for funding via contestable funding or through the EoI process.

Building capacity and capability in engagement in the DSC community was an ongoing activity, carried out through recurring socialisation of the engagement concept whenever there were new

members of the leadership team, newly funded research projects or new key liaisons with MBIE. The Communications and Engagement Plan, for example, was targeted at DSC researchers and, like the EoI process, was designed both to capture information and also to build capacity – i.e., it was a mechanism that encouraged DSC researchers to consider and discuss how to integrate engagement into their proposed projects. The Engagement Programme also built engagement capacity and capability within the DSC’s leadership structure by, for example, briefing and preparing for meetings between the DSC Director and sector leaders and facilitating productive conversations between members of the DSC Board and the RUG.

We deliberately share here examples of this invisible, “gluing behind the scenes” work, which often takes years to pay off, as it builds the groundwork, enables, advocates for, and creates, a receptive environment that is key for delivery of a successful programme of engagement.

3. Definitional and process challenges

Here we explore challenges that we regard as being internal to the establishment and delivery of science engagement. (This is in contrast with the external forces, such as institutional and political context, discussed in the next section.) We suggest these have relevance to any engagement practitioner or team intent on delivering theoretically informed, strategic engagement that is embedded within a science research programme, with particular relevance to applied or mission-led research (for example, engagement about climate, health, environment, new technologies) on any scale from an individual lab to national or international consortia. We highlight here two aspects in particular: challenges related to conflicting assumptions about

engagement (a definitional challenge) and those related to conflicting timescales (a process challenge).

3.1 The challenge of conflicting assumptions about engagement

Many of our recurring challenges were related to either disagreement about the role of engagement, or a lack of skills required for engagement about difficult choices.

While we had gone to great effort to explain and give explicit examples of our expectations for engagement (and gained sign-off for these at SLT and Board levels), we found repeatedly that our leadership, new researchers, external partners and funders were guided instead by their own assumptions and expectations of engagement that conflicted with ours.

For example, the Governance Board, host organisation and government funding agency expected the Engagement Programme to include marketing and public relations for the DSC as a whole. This included branding and profile, reputation management and justification of impact. In this context, many of our actions—which prioritised meaningful engagement about climate change issues over “brand awareness”—were seen to be underselling or poorly representing the Challenge. In response to this tension, and critical feedback from the funder, we appointed a senior communications advisor to meet these expectations.

We learnt an important lesson through this experience. While our aspirational engagement goal to inform decision-making about climate change was lauded on paper, and applauded by the review panels, it could not be delivered at the expense of more traditional communications and marketing that attended to the need or desire of the research programme, partner institutions and funding agency for positive publicity.

The process of delivering our Engagement Programme also revealed that professionals who are passionate and skilled in delivering science engagement and communication do not necessarily have the skill-set required, or the inclination, to deliver engagement about difficult choices, which is, ultimately, where our adaptation focus lay. Information about our funding opportunities was primarily promoted around and accessible to the national climate-change communication and science communication communities. As a result, the proposals that we received were similar to work that already existed in this space: art exhibitions, podcasts, science-education activities in schools, entertaining hands-on science exhibits, etc., none of which aligned well with our engagement objectives. While we sought careful facilitation and engagement about the difficult choices climate change would force on New Zealanders and that could usefully be informed by climate research, this is not what science communicators traditionally have the experience, skills or interest in delivering. In retrospect, it would perhaps have been better to reach out to environmental planners, climate risk managers (such as insurers, banks, and Ministries) and others whose professional focus includes facilitation of complex decision-making involving uncertainty and conflicting interests and assist them to apply their skills to climate-change adaptation, rather than to expect communicators who knew about climate change to develop skills and methods in these difficult conversations.

3.2 Conflicting timeframes of science and engagement

Another internal challenge, which may resonate across many science/engagement disciplines and fields, relates to the differing timescales of science and engagement. We provide three examples here.

The Engagement Programme was committed to using DSC science “to assist sectors and communities across the country to make better-informed decisions in areas that will be impacted by climate change” (Salmon & Goven, 2017, p. 4). In addition, the Engagement Strategy prioritised enabling a wide range of New Zealanders to inform DSC’s research agenda. Both turned out to be impracticable.

The Engagement Programme was expected both to be active from the start of the DSC *and* to use DSC science, including (with some delay) results from the NZESM to assist New Zealanders to make better-informed decisions. DSC research results and NZESM projections (in particular) would not, however, be available for several years into the Programme. While this may be typical of large computer modelling endeavours, it meant that the Engagement Programme had to find other relevant science with which to engage in the interim, which placed it at odds with the Board, who insisted that the Engagement Programme focus on DSC research rather than climate change science more generally.

With regard to enabling New Zealanders to inform DSC’s research agenda, we encountered a commonplace problem. The science funding system generally asks for a substantial amount of detail on the research that will be undertaken prior to it being funded. While this is not unreasonable, it does not leave any (or much) scope for new (or altered) research priorities that might emerge from engagement. The Dialogues presented an alternative to this scenario, but: 1) this did not address the problem as it applied more generally to the Engagement Programme; and 2) the Dialogues also ran into resistance on this score (described below).

Finally, much foundational engagement work is slow relative to expectations that might be held around engagement impact. This needs to be anticipated and potentially defended from the start.

It requires building new relationships, establishing trust, and discovering who the influencers or advocates are within different organisations and communities (examples of ‘invisible outputs’). Scheduling meetings, sharing in cultural and institutional conventions such as coffee meetings and lunches, writing one-page briefings for a manager, and organising stakeholder events take time. This work can be hard to quantify or justify in terms of outputs in the first year of starting but over time will prove invaluable and can lead to ambitious and innovative collaborations.

The timescale of engagement can therefore be experienced as too fast compared to that of scientific research, too slow compared to expectations related to impact, and misaligned with the timescale and culture of funding systems.

4. Challenges of political and institutional context

Scientific research is increasingly “big” and multidisciplinary (or interdisciplinary) and multi-institutional. Funders often favour multi-institutional collaborations, and addressing “wicked problems” may require them. It is also the case that, over the past four decades, scientific research institutions the world over, as in New Zealand, have undergone changes in organisation and purpose that can be characterised as neo-liberalisation (Lave et al., 2010). Thus, we have reason to believe that the political and institutional challenges we describe here may have general relevance even if the details vary.

The DSC was the product of a political process, both in the sense that the formation of National Science Challenges was a political and policy priority of the government of the day and in the sense that it involved a struggle among institutions and scientists for scarce resources along with compromise, negotiation, and appeasement. Many feared that if their research area was not

incorporated into a NSC, it would mean the end of public funding for their research. Aspects of the DSC, including its name, were products of the fact that the original research framing of this NSC was centred around the connection between the climate and Antarctica. Following an international review process of a first proposal, which focused on Antarctic research, the associated research community was instructed to revise the proposal to focus more heavily on climate-change impacts and adaptation. Considerable climate-related Antarctic research remained, but the NZESM became the major focus. The early choice – it is unclear whether this was in response to a signal from Government or a preference of the researchers who wrote the unsuccessful first bid – to ignore climate-change mitigation applied to DSC engagement as well as research. Engaging with communities on climate change while avoiding issues of mitigation was challenging as it restricted our ability to fully respond to engagement requests and opportunities for collaboration.

As noted above, the DSC is hosted by a Crown Research Institute (CRI). CRIs are the product of a major reorganisation of public science in New Zealand in the 1990s, as a result of which public and governmental research agencies were disbanded and CRIs were created. CRIs are state-owned limited-liability companies intended “to undertake research” with the proviso that the “research undertaken by a Crown Research Institute should be undertaken for the benefit of New Zealand” (Crown Research Institutes Act, 1992). They were organised along corporate lines with highly autonomous CEOs and were expected to generate “dividends” for the government. The nature of this “science dividend” was ambiguous from the beginning (Poletti, 2004), sometimes but not always interpreted by the government of the day as a financial return on investment. Current guidance states: “Dividends are expected from CRIs unless the CRI has a greater need for reinvestment. The level of estimated dividends is set by the board in line with

discussions with the shareholding ministers through the Statement of Corporate Intent (SCI) and business plan consultation process” (*Monitoring and Indicators for CRIs*, n.d.)

CRIs were originally made almost entirely dependent on short-to-medium term contestable funding, generating hyper-competitive and anti-collaborative practices that focused on generating company profits (sometimes by selling research offshore) rather than public-good research benefits (Davenport & Bibby, 2007). As early as 1998, a report commissioned by the government notes concerns about “the extent to which the commercial objectives of CRIs are perceived to be overriding their objectives of achieving benefits for New Zealand”, including by “restricting access to the results of PGSF [Public Good Science Fund – then the largest pool of public science funding] research in an endeavour to commercialise it and capture the benefits from it for themselves” (Hodgson, Howe, Saunders & Winsley, 1998, as cited in Hunt, 2003, p. 26). These problems persisted through regular attempts to reform the system, and in 2009 the government appointed a task force to review the CRIs. Its report noted:

Currently, it is not clear if a CRI’s objective is to create value for itself, as a company, or to generate value for New Zealand. Current ownership arrangements seem to place undue emphasis on research and development that produces outputs that individual CRIs can capture in their statements of revenue and balance sheets, rather than on research that contributes to the wellbeing and prosperity of New Zealand... The measure of a CRI’s success should be the positive impact it has on New Zealand – be that economic, social or environmental – not the commercial return a CRI has been able to achieve... CRIs were set up to address enduring challenges and opportunities that New Zealand faces.

(Crown Research Institute Taskforce, 2010, pp. 7–8)

The task force emphasised the need for greater inter-institutional collaboration, and recommended that the government dedicate a portion of its science funding to “major national collaborative challenges” that “would provide incentives for collaboration in new multi-disciplinary areas of research” (Crown Research Institute Taskforce, 2010, p. 30); this resulted in the creation of the NSCs.

Thus, the NSCs, mission-focused and collaborative (in concept), can be seen as the latest attempt to counteract the perverse incentives resulting from the restructuring of public science. However, as the CRIs were major players in the formation of NSCs, and CRIs remained largely unchanged, their characteristics left their mark on NSCs as well. (For a discussion of these issues in relation to a different NSC, see Baisden (2018).)

Moreover, the NSCs, consistent with the overall corporatisation of science in New Zealand, are overseen by Governance Boards often weighted toward corporate/business leaders and sometimes, as in the DSC’s case, lacking expertise in the NSCs’ mission areas (in this case, climate change), yet who are empowered to dictate to the science leadership. The DSC’s Board also included the CEO of the host institution. As an observer member, he did not have voting rights but engaged in debate around decisions and was present during voting. (He has since been made a full member of the Board.)

In the case of the DSC, an independent science panel was also established, whom the Board could consult in their decision-making but whose views did not bind the Board. The day-to-day management of research was carried out by the Director and science leadership team (SLT), made up of the leaders of the five research programmes, of which Engagement was one.

Research and engagement in the DSC therefore occurred not only within the complex historical and political backdrop of the Challenge itself (including unclear power relationships between the Board, the leadership team and MBIE) but also within struggles over resources and priorities among institutions. As discussed above, engagement can be interpreted in many different ways, and within this complex system there were many implicit as well as explicit expectations and assumptions around the role of engagement and communications. In addition, there were (sometimes shifting) power relations between all of these institutions related to their history and the distribution of funding. These tensions and power relationships are an important part of the context within which the scientific research and engagement were occurring. In the case of the physical-science research projects, most of the researchers could remain largely unaware of most of these tensions and politics. While they may have been asked for occasional reports and updates to serve the needs of these structures, the delivery of their research, once funded, was not, on the whole, impacted in a tangible way by these jostling power structures. It was our observation that the three programmes with more social-science research or direct engagement with communities – Impacts and Implications, Vision Mātauranga and Engagement – experienced greater impacts from this political-institutional context. We provide here two examples in which the exercise of power through these structures impinged on Engagement activities in unexpected ways.

First, in response to what we understood was an expectation by MBIE that we raise the DSC's profile and increase stakeholder engagement (discussed above), particularly in Auckland (NZ's largest city), we organised a targeted stakeholder engagement event in conjunction with the high-profile closing feature of the Auckland Arts Festival – the projection of hours of life-size video of an Antarctic iceberg wrapped around Auckland Museum together with an original soundtrack

(Michael, 2017). We nonetheless had some concerns about elements of our role with this event, and so the proposal passed through several iterations and discussions prior to approval of funding by the SLT. Notably, in approving the event, the SLT cited the need to increase the DSC's profile and the need to mitigate the risk of competing organisations having the profile if we didn't, even though these were not objectives contained in the approved Engagement Strategy.

After committing to this event on the condition that we were the only science partner, we experienced a direct, last-minute intervention from the Board, whose role is high-level governance, not vetting individual engagement activities. There was no explanation given as to why this event in particular required additional Board-level scrutiny as compared to other engagement events that the Engagement Programme organised with stakeholders (all of which were passed via the SLT). This activity fell comfortably within the boundaries of the Board-approved Engagement Strategy. The objection was that the event posed 'reputational risk'. Although the nature of this risk was not clearly spelt out, there was concern among some Auckland-based members of the Board that, because the event was on a Friday, the stakeholders whose attendance they regarded as necessary for the event to be seen as successful would not attend: Wellingtonians' willingness to attend such (politics- or policy-infused) events whenever they were held was contrasted to Aucklanders' preference for socialising and sport. Auckland-based members of the Board appeared to regard this potential failure in Auckland as a personal reputational risk.

The Auckland location and high profile of the event suddenly became liabilities. The final result was that the stakeholder event was cancelled at the last minute and replaced by much more general, and low-key, public outreach that would have been unlikely to be funded according to our normal criteria. The ability and willingness of the Board to intervene in our activities

demonstrated in a frustrating and unsettling way that there were power structures beyond our control and our planning that could unexpectedly redefine the acceptable boundaries of engagement. While managing risk is a legitimate activity of the Board, it is important to the functionality of the programme that this is carried out through guidelines and standard processes rather than ad-hoc, last-minute interventions. There were no existing guidelines or processes that were violated by this activity.

Reflection on this experience surfaced a number of implicit objectives that the Engagement team had been using in our decision-making, which were not articulated in our strategy. For example, “shift the narrative” had become an implicit objective as we responded to the nature of the applications for funding that we received. We recognised the value of contributing to events that would happen anyway, in order, for example, to push an existing Antarctica-centric “penguins and paleo” narrative toward a “climate-change impacts in NZ” one. There were also implicit objectives that we might call “meeting our masters’ expectations”, applying in our case to both MBIE and the Board. Signals from MBIE, the Board, the ISP and other institutions involved with the DSC therefore had the potential to require us to attend to additional – and conflicting – objectives, which could also make it more difficult to meet the Engagement Programme’s explicit objectives.

The second example is a chain of events that redefined the entire scope of the DSC, with a particular impact on social-science research (in Impacts & Implications) and engagement. In the second round of Contestable Funding, a top-ranked proposal focused on legal aspects of adaptation. Despite this endorsement from the SLT, the Board ruled the subject out of scope and reallocated the funding to a much lower-ranked physical-science proposal. Not long after, the Board also refused to allow funding of a subsequent research proposal, which had been approved

by the SLT, for a research question produced by one of the Dialogues. At about the same time, discussions began about the second five-year phase of the DSC (assuming funding was renewed). Acting on significant input from key policy stakeholders as well as the success of the Dialogues in sparking sectoral and media discussion of adaptation challenges, the SLT produced proposals for the next stage that would continue to develop the adaptation discussions and link the scientific research more closely to the needs of those making adaptation decisions. These were also informed by two programme-specific workshops with researchers within DSC. The Board responded by issuing a new, one-page “scope” directive outlining that the work of the DSC in the second phase would focus more narrowly on building and using outputs from the NZESM, thereby ruling out of scope the SLT’s proposals. This thoroughly undermined the Dialogues, which were created to identify research needs related to impacts and adaptation. In addition, given that any results from the NZESM were still years away, this focus on the NZESM and its outputs sharply narrowed the acceptable field of activities for engagement in ways that were incompatible with our own programme goals.

Among the lessons of these examples is that governance of research matters. In this case, the inclusion on the Board of the CEO of the host institution (and none of the other participating institutions) creates a clear conflict of interest, as the decisions of the Board are likely to impact the revenue of that institution. The DSC is not the only NSC in which this occurs, and it is surprising that it is permitted by MBIE (who provide ultimate oversight of governance arrangements).

As discussed above, the NSCs were established in part to overcome the obstacles to public-good-focused collaboration posed by the institutional interests of CRIs. Yet in this case governance

arrangements allowed those institutional interests to prevail: the host institution, as the home of the NZESM, stood to gain significantly from this change in scope.

Governance of research has particular implications for more public-facing and policy-adjacent activities, including engagement. Research and engagement linked to decision- and policy-making are more likely to be interpreted by non-expert Board members as partisan or ideological and therefore opposed, whether as inherently illegitimate for a scientific research programme or as hostile to their own views. While others may not work under Boards like these, all large research endeavours have power centres and hierarchies, even if power is held among researchers themselves (all of whom must respond to institutional imperatives).

These examples also highlight a more general problem in the engagement field: many people do not see engagement as research-based and therefore consider themselves competent to pronounce on engagement (and perhaps social science) in ways they would not with regard to the physical sciences. This means that non-experts may not only be inclined to regard some engagement as inappropriately political, they may also feel justified in superimposing their views over an expertise they do not recognise. For engagement practitioners attached to large research projects, understanding how power operates in the project may suggest possible interventions to secure protection of the integrity of one's work, or it may suggest exercising caution with regard to how and what one promises to those public or stakeholder participants with whom one attempts to engage (Salmon & Roop, 2019).

5. At the intersection of definitional and context challenges: The fate of evaluation

When we developed the DSC Engagement Programme, we intended to take engagement seriously, both as a practice that can and should be done well and as a practice about which a body of research (regarding what it means to do engagement well) exists to which we might add (Salmon et al., 2017). To that end, we included a Research and Evaluation objective in the engagement strategy and funded work to evaluate the success of activities carried out by, or with the support of, the Engagement Programme.

We envisioned evaluation as (a) correcting the tendency in outreach/engagement to substitute metrics like attendance for any effort to assess whether one's goals (if one had even articulated any) were met; (b) taking engagement, and the EP, seriously enough to want to drive improvements in it; and (c) contributing to research on engagement.

As noted above (see section 2.2), one of the challenges we faced was the Board's expectation that the Engagement Programme would deliver marketing and public relations for the DSC. Despite our efforts to advocate for our own approach to engagement, over time and with shifts in personnel (both in DSC leadership and within the Engagement Programme), this expectation grew stronger. As the Engagement Programme increasingly sought to demonstrate to the Board its effective performance of this role, there grew within the Engagement Programme a need for what could be called the marketing and public relations of the Engagement Programme itself—to the SLT, the Board, and MBIE. Evaluation that was oriented toward understanding and learning from failures as well as successes, rather than recording successes for reports to the governance

structure, was at odds with this and increasingly seen as unhelpful. Evaluation effectively became obsolete, and the evaluation workstream was discontinued.

6. Conclusion

From our experience of a well-funded engagement programme within a major national research consortium, we have drawn a number of lessons that we think have broad relevance for engagement practitioners.

High-quality engagement requires a great deal of ‘invisible’ preparatory and maintenance work. Engagement practitioners answerable to managers of whatever kind (including Boards, funders, PIs, etc.) may need not only to explicitly build in time (as well as funding) for this invisible work, but also to educate the managers about its necessity from the inception of the proposal and throughout the project (more invisible work!).

Expectations of, and assumptions about, engagement may be strongly held both by practitioners and by those with little or no expertise in the field. While we were clear, and explicit, about the type of engagement we sought, we did not sufficiently account for the degree to which some practitioners would nonetheless remain attached to their preferred view, or simply be unable to deliver a different kind of engagement. When it comes to recruiting practitioners to develop and deliver engagement activities we learned that seeking skill sets and experience appropriate to the type of engagement sought is more important than subject knowledge, which is perhaps more easily learned to the needed degree.

Expectations of engagement held by those with little or no expertise, whether they be researchers or managers, are likely to create the necessity for ongoing (invisible!) education efforts by the

engagement practitioners. This includes making explicit the unavoidable misalignment of the timescales and processes of engagement with those of funding agencies and scientific research projects, and with demands for immediate impact. When those with little expertise nonetheless have power over engagement-practitioner activities, education is vital but may not be sufficient. The inclination to regard engagement as risky, partisan, and/or non-expert makes engagement vulnerable to intervention by those ‘managers’ with relatively unaccountable power. Early efforts to establish explicit guidelines and processes for how engagement is overseen may (or may not) be protective. Political and institutional context will likely precipitate a power structure that shapes these challenges and the likelihood of overcoming them.

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Ethics Statement:

Due to the developmental nature of this programme, and associated research, we completed Human Ethics Applications for specific activities as they arose, including for surveys and interviews with specific groups, and evaluation of specific events. These were approved through the Victoria University of Wellington Human Ethics Committee as applications 22369 (NZ Climate Change Engagement Survey) 25821(Capacity-building workshops), 26861 (Evaluation of the Deep South Dialogues) and 22369 (interviews about the political and institutional context of engagement).

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